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SUSTAINABLE INVESTMENT FUNDS AND RECENT DEVELOPEMENTS IN THE EUROPEAN UNION

Abstract: *In this paper, the author presents the results of empirical research on the regulatory framework of sustainable investment funds in the European Union (EU).*

The first part of the paper provides a historical overview of their regulations and a detailed analysis of the EU's Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR), which are followed by a more detailed elaboration on similar legal sources that further regulate areas of sustainable investment funds.

In the second part of the paper, the author explains the grounds for the potential improvements within the regulatory framework of sustainable investment funds, with the aim of ensuring more suitable investor protection and sufficient protection against greenwashing practices.

Keywords: *EU, sustainable investment funds, SFDR.*

1. Introduction

In 2015, the EU started a new mission of creating a sustainable future and becoming the first climate-neutral region by 2050. The Paris Agreement

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(2015)¹ and the United Nations (UN) 2030 Agenda (2015)² represent the main international frameworks addressing global challenges prioritizing the overall sustainability and climate actions. Both share similar goals, such as: (i) combating climate change; (ii) sustainable development; (iii) international cooperation; (iv) equity and inclusion; (v) transparency; (vi) monitoring; and (vii) accountability. However, their scope, implementation mechanisms and legal powers³ differ.

The Paris Agreement (2015) is an international treaty on climate change which was adopted by 195 Parties at the UN Climate Change Conference in Paris, on 12 December 2015, and entered into force on 4 November 2016. It provides a global framework which has a direct effect on the approach to sustainability and climate-related risks by governments, investors and in-scope entities.

The UN Sustainable Development Goals⁴ (SDGs) were adopted by all UN Member States at a historic UN summit in September 2015 and came into effect on 1 January 2016. The SDGs represent a comprehensive model for tackling the world's most pressing challenges and aims to be a global guide within this area by 2030.

Built on EU's 2015 mission, as part of its sustainability goal, the European Green Deal⁵ is the EU strategy launched in 2019. The EU has had multiple initiatives ever since, including the reform of its legal framework, in an effort to successfully reduce its emissions in the amount of 55% by the year 2030, and ultimately achieve climate neutrality by 2050. However, such plan and strategy raised some questions as, based on the Eurostat⁶ and other official reports, in 2015 the EU's gas emissions were around 10% on the global

¹ UN (2015). Paris Agreement, United Nations; for more, see: https://unfccc.int/files/essential_background/convention/application/pdf/english_paris_agreement.pdf

² The United Nations/UN (2015). The UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, A/RES/70/1, UN, New York; <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/21252030%20Agenda%20for%20Sustainable%20Development%20web.pdf>

³ While the Paris Agreement is a legally binding international treaty, the UN 2030 Agenda is a non-binding political commitment.

⁴ Hwang, S., Kim J. (2017). United Nations and Sustainable Development Goals (UN and SDGs): A Handbook for Youth, UNESCAP East and North-East Asia Office, Incheon, Republic of Korea, 2017; see: <https://www.local2030.org/library/302/UN-and-SDGs-A-handbook-for-youth.pdf>

⁵ European Council (2025). European Green Deal; <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/european-green-deal/>

⁶ Eurostat (2025). Domestic net greenhouse gas emissions (Online data code:sdg_13_10), 13.5.2015; see: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/sdg_13_10/default/table?lang=en

scale.⁷ Thus, one may question if the accomplishment of such sustainable goals within the set deadline would have noticeable effect and impact on the planet as a whole.

2. Legal framework in the EU

Over the last decade, the EU has been actively working on re-orienting private capital to more sustainable long-term investments within its financial system and EU's Capital Market Union (EC, 2018: 2).⁸ In 2018, the EU released its action plan for financing sustainable growth, which contained a broader strategy, aimed to mobilize finance for sustainable growth and address climate change (Möslein, Sørensen, 2018: 221). EU's normative framework for sustainable investment funds was introduced as a consequence of the aforesaid international frameworks.

The Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR)⁹ of the European Parliament and the Council was published in June 2020 and came into effect in March 2021. The main objective of the SFDR was to improve transparency and disclosure requirements within the financial sector and its participants (Hummel, Jobst, 2024: 320). It was specifically designed to protect the sustainable investment products by implementing corporate sustainability reporting and due diligence, and was considered as the leading framework for the European financial markets between 2019–2022 (Birindelli, Chiappini, Jalal, 2023: 56). *Inter alia*, the SFDR introduced some

⁷ The analyses is based on the Eustadt's report (4.4b tones of CO₂ gas emissions) as compared to the UN Environment program (https://wesr.unep.org/media/docs/theme/13/EGR_2015_Technical_Report_final_version.pdf), and joint publication by PBL Netherlands and European Commission's Joint Research Center (https://www.researchgate.net/profile/G-Janssens-Maenhout/publication/284644287_Trends_in_Global_CO2_emissions_2015_report/links/5655b21308aefe619b1ae8c4/Trends-in-Global-CO2-emissions-2015-report.pdf) as compared to the US EPA Climate Change indicators (<https://www.epa.gov/climate-indicators/greenhouse-gases>), where it is indicated that the global CO₂ gas emissions were in the amount between 35.7b - 47b tones. Therefore, based on the information contained in the three listed reports and regardless of the question of accuracy of the data provided by the individual countries, if the EU's emissions were c. 4.4b tones, that would make 9.6 - 12.32 % on the global scale.

⁸ European Commission (EC). Sustainable finance: Commission's Action Plan for a greener and cleaner economy EC Press release, Brussels, 8 March 2018, p.2; https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/api/files/document/print/en/ip_18_1404/IP_18_1404_EN.pdf

⁹ Regulation (EU) 2019/2088 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2019 on sustainability-related disclosures in the financial services sector; PE/87/2019/REV/1; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/2088/oj/eng>

improvements: (i) mandatory sustainability products classification¹⁰; (ii) regulatory technical standards (RTS)¹¹; (iii) mandatory transparency of information to investors¹²; and (iv) principal adverse impact analyses (PAIs).¹³ Those improvements were expected to be implemented at two levels: (i) the entity level, and (ii) the product level. At the entity level, disclosures would need to be published on its website; at the product level, disclosures would need to be published on its website and in the pre-contractual disclosures. When applicable, some products would also need to publish (on its website and in the pre-contractual disclosures) additional special disclosures when promoting environmental, social and governance (ESG) characteristics and/or taxonomy disclosures explaining which ESG characteristics would promote environmental objectives.

For the purpose of ensuring better investor protection, the EU legal framework obliged the financial and non-financial entities to share a common definition of economic activities which would be deemed environmentally sustainable, by introducing the EU Taxonomy Act in 2020.¹⁴ The Taxonomy Act represents a key part of EU's sustainable strategy as it has managed to standardize the framework for identifying which economic activities are objectively sustainable. It introduces a classification system for the economic activities considered as sustainable investments and provides technical screening criteria.

¹⁰ The funds can be classified as follows: Article 6 SFDR - Funds without a sustainability scope (grey funds); Article 8 - Funds that promote environmental or social characteristics (light green), and Article 9 - Funds that have sustainable investment as their objective (dark green).

¹¹ Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/1288 of 6 April 2022 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2019/2088 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to regulatory technical standards specifying the details of the content and presentation of the information in relation to the principle of 'do no significant harm', specifying the content, methodologies and presentation of information in relation to sustainability indicators and adverse sustainability impacts, and the content and presentation of the information in relation to the promotion of environmental or social characteristics and sustainable investment objectives in pre-contractual documents, on websites and in periodic reports; C/2022/1931; https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_del/2022/1288/oj/eng

¹² Art.23 SFDR-Pre contractual investors disclosures within the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/1288.

¹³ Art. 4 SFDR -Transparency of adverse sustainability impacts at entity level.

¹⁴ Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2020 on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/2088; PE/20/2020/INIT; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2020/852/oj/eng>

With the intention of extending the sustainability goal's reach to a larger number of entities (including non-EU funds with significant EU operations), the EU has adopted the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CRSD) in 2022.¹⁵ The CRSD obliges the funds to significantly increase the transparency of their disclosure on impacts, risks and opportunities (IROs) that are deemed material for the business or its value chain.

Additionally, the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD)¹⁶ was adopted in 2024 with the aim to mandate the (EU and non-EU) funds to foster sustainable and responsible corporate behavior by identifying, preventing, and mitigating adverse human rights and environmental impacts within their operations and value chains.

Finally, with the intention to supplement the SFDR, including among others the technical aspects of the disclosure requirements (for financial market participants, advisors and their related financial products), the EU Commission adopted the SFDR Delegated Regulation (SFDR Level 2)¹⁷ in 2022, which entered into force in January 2023. In order to adequately inform the investors, the amendments legally bind the sustainable investment funds and their investment fund managers to disclose any environmentally sustainable fossil gas and nuclear-related activities which their financial products invest in. Within those disclosures, the funds are obliged to present their PAIs, fulfill the RTS, prevent greenwashing, and state whether the products comply with the “do no significant harm” (DNSH) principle for any ESG objectives.

As a result, the investors are taking into consideration the non-financial factors impacting the ESG sectors. Even with the similar factor of “moral returns” within the ethical and ESG investments, they are not the same as the ethical investments do not consider ESG characteristics as a priority in the decision making process.

¹⁵ Directive (EU) 2022/2464 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 amending Regulation (EU) No 537/2014, Directive 2004/109/EC, Directive 2006/43/EC and Directive 2013/34/EU, as regards corporate sustainability reporting; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2022/2464/oj/eng>

¹⁶ Directive (EU) 2024/1760 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 on corporate sustainability due diligence and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937 and Regulation (EU) 2023/2859; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2024/1760/oj/eng>

¹⁷ Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/1288 of 6 April 2022, C/2022/1931.

3. SFDR'S ESG investment products

Sustainability in the EU framework represents a mixture of a sustainable investment,¹⁸ sustainability factors,¹⁹ and sustainability risk.²⁰ A sustainable investment contributes to either environmental or social objectives, without causing significant harm within its objectives, and the fund follows good governance practices. Integration of the ESG factors within the fund's strategy remains the most popular and fastest-growing approach of sustainable investment (Amini, Rahmani, 2023: 1287). Socially responsible investing (SRI) is a heterogeneous form of investing, most commonly characterized by an adherence to non-financial ESG issues within the decision making process (Baure, Smeets, 2015: 117).

However, despite the benefits it entails, the term ESG has not been defined in terms of universally accepted standards. It is often defined as a novel term similar to SRI and corporate social responsibility (CSR), or as a set of additional non-financial investment goals of an entity and/or a product (Heidorn, Watermeyer, Haar, 2023: 4). Nevertheless, the SFDR has harmonized rules for the classification of the fund's products that are available in the EU's financial market. It introduces the modalities and explicitly provides information necessary for a clear taxonomy based on the declaration regarding the integration of ESG factors at the asset manager level (Distefano, Gentile, Cucurachi, De Iaco, 2024:1).

The three main products categories under the SFDR include: (i) Article 6 fund, (ii) Article 8 fund, and (iii) Article 9 fund. The first one has objectives which are not aligned with the ESG themes which would be considered as funds *without a sustainability scope*; the second one's interest is *directed towards ESG themes but does not represent the main criteria* of the fund, while the last one's *main objective is to comply with ESG issues* (Distefano, Gentile, Cucurachi, De Iaco, 2024: 1). On that basis, the 3 groups of products recognized by the SFDR are most commonly referred to as *grey* (Art. 6), *light green* (Art. 8), and *dark green* (Art. 9). As the green products (i.e. Articles 8 and 9) have overall sustainability objectives which are in line with the ESG themes (i.e. concepts such as PAIs, sustainability risks, "taxonomy aligned", "sustainable characteristics", Characteristics depending on the "level" of their compliance), they are commonly referred to as "light green" and "dark green" funds (Muñoz, Lamandini, 2024: 10). The main difference between the green products is their level of "greenness", which is assessed and classified based

¹⁸ Art. 2 (17) of the SFDR.

¹⁹ Art. 2 (24) of the SFDR.

²⁰ Art. 2 (22) of the SFDR.

on the type of financial products and their underlying investment options' compliance with the Characteristics (Spaans, Derwall, Huij, Koedijk, 2024: 8).

Thus, an Article 8 product, as a *light green* fund, has to meet specific requirements: (i) it must fulfill the threshold of at least 80% compliance with the Characteristics (ESMA 2024:6)²¹; (ii) it may include ESG factors in the investment decisions; (iii) it does not have to hold sustainable investments but should promote ESG characteristics; (iv) it may use the exclusion criteria when screening; (v) it has optional PAI and DNSH reporting; (vi) it is not required to be aligned with the EU Taxonomy; and (vii) it may have a portfolio of sustainable and non-sustainable investments. On the other hand, the Article 9 product is considered a *dark-green* fund which must meet the following requirements: (i) full compliance with the Characteristics²²; (ii) include ESG factors in the investment decisions; (iii) hold sustainable investments strongly encouraged to be aligned with the EU Taxonomy; (iv) report its PAIs; (v) comply with the DNSH principle; and (vi) ensure compliance with the stricter transparency and disclosure rules.²³

4. Greenwashing

In the event of misuse of the EU's sustainable framework, a common issue known as greenwashing may occur within the scope of sustainability as green initiatives. Greenwashing is a practice of misleading investors by means of falsely claimed engagements within the ESG sector and sustainable investments. This can be done in multiple ways, such as by presenting to the investors misleading investor disclosures, inappropriate ESG labels, false transparency, and regulatory non-compliance with sustainability standards.

Simultaneously, with the growth of ESG investments, more asset managers are attracting retail investors by presenting their products as sustainable, while lacking objective qualifications for their claims (Musciano, 2022: 433). Consequently, the high demand from the investors for socially responsible investment products may lead to greenwashing by asset managers (Raghunandan, Rajgopal, 2022: 827). In practice, the greenwashed products would most commonly disclose: (i) inconsistent ESG terminology and imagery; (ii) misalignment between their claims and real investments; (iii) poor quality and/or complexly written disclosures; and (iv) organizationally weak structures.

²¹ ESMA (2024). Final Report Guidelines on funds' names using ESG or sustainability-related terms, European Securities and Markets Authority/ESMA, 14 May 2024; https://www.esma.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2024-05/ESMA34-472-440_Final_Report_Guidelines_on_funds_names.pdf

²² Article 2 (17) SFDR.

²³ Article 8 SFDR.

At the EU level, legal framework has been undergoing a revision in order to properly tackle the greenwashing issue. One of the mechanisms is the Directive for Empowering consumers for the Green Transition (2024)²⁴ whose objective is to empower the investors to have stronger rights with the aim of helping EU move forward its climate neutrality goal by 2050.²⁵

At the EU member states level, in order to stop the greenwashing practice national regulators, such as *Commission de Surveillance du Secteur Financier* (CSSF) in Luxembourg, have expressed their concerns and issued supervision strategies to prevent greenwashing. For example, the CSSF indicated their prioritization of (i) disclosure oversight, (ii) risk-based supervision, (iii) MiFiD II²⁶ integration, and (iv) portfolio consistency (CSSF, 2024).²⁷

5. Methods of ensuring fund compliance

The SFDR requires from all funds to appropriately disclose information on: (i) how they take ESG risks into account; and (ii) the potential impact of those risks on the value of investments (Darpeix, Demartini, 2021: 4). By obliging the funds and their management companies (AIFM/ManCo) to provide reliable and comparable ESG data and to enable investors to make more informed investment decisions, the market becomes more transparent. The disclosures can be divided into two groups: at the product level, and at the level of financial market participants (FMP). Product level types include web-site disclosures, pre-contractual disclosures and periodic reports. The FMP types include policy on integration of sustainability risks within the manager's investment decision-making process, alignment of the remuneration policy with sustainability risks and adverse sustainability impact.

²⁴ Directive (EU) 2024/825 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 February 2024 amending Directives 2005/29/EC and 2011/83/EU as regards empowering consumers for the green transition through better protection against unfair practices and through better information; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2024/825/oj/eng>

²⁵ European Commission/EC (2020). Committing to climate-neutrality by 2050: Commission proposes European Climate Law and consults on the European Climate Pact; EC Press release, Brussels, 4 March 2020; https://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/230214/EU_commitment%20to%20climate-neutrality_by_2050.pdf

²⁶ Directive 2014/65/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 May 2014 on markets in financial instruments and amending Directive 2002/92/EC and Directive 2011/61/EU ("the second Markets in Financial Instruments Directive"); <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2014/65/oj/eng>

²⁷ CSSF (2024). The CSSF's supervisory priorities in the area of sustainable finance, 22 March 2024; <https://www.cssf.lu/en/2024/03/the-cssfs-supervisory-priorities-in-the-area-of-sustainable-finance/>

The disclosures may be included in: (i) the fund's prospectus within the pre-contractual investment disclosures; (ii) the fund's official web-site which may be disclosed: (a) within the wording of the fund's prospectus, or (b) in the periodic reports. In the event of Undertakings for Collective Investment in Transferable Securities (UCITS), additional documentation would need to be secured in order to tailor them for the retail investors, such as the key investor information document (KIID)²⁸ and packaged retail investment products (PRIIPS)²⁹ (Petrocelli, 2015: 1). In order to apply the same standard in the alternative investment funds (AIF), regulatory changes were made by introducing the PRIIPS Regulation.³⁰ The original UCITS PRIIPS was extended from an investment product only to insurance-based products; thus, it was thus revised into packaged retail and insurance-based investment products (PRIIPS).

Moreover, the UCITS KID was also extended to key information document (KID) which presents a current standard for all PRIIPS including the UCITS funds. Within the initial SFDR (2019), the investor disclosures were originally placed in Article 8, which prescribed the set of requirements that would need to be shared with the investor³¹ (Roncone, Massari, 2024:10). However, upon coming into force of the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/1288, pre-contractual investor disclosure regime was set in Article 23³² (Scheitza, Busch, 2024: 2). This article determines the set of manda-

²⁸ Article 78 of Directive 2009/65/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 on the coordination of laws, regulations and administrative provisions relating to undertakings for collective investment in transferable securities (UCITS); <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2009/65/oj/eng>

²⁹ Regulation (EU) No 1286/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 November 2014 on key information documents for packaged retail and insurance-based investment products.

³⁰ Regulation (EU) No 1286/2014; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2014/1286/oj/eng>

³¹ This included: (i) the mandatory template which was in the Annex II of the SFDR, and (ii) the explanation on whether the characteristics are met, whether sustainable investments are made, and whether the "do not harm" principle is ensured.

³² Article 23 of the SFDR (2019), titled "Website section for the disclosure of sustainability-related information about financial products" specifies: "*Financial market participants shall, for each financial product, publish the information referred to in Article 10(1) of Regulation (EU) 2019/2088 in a separate section titled, 'Sustainability-related disclosures', in the same part of their website as the other information relating to the financial product, including marketing communications. Financial market participants shall clearly identify the financial product to which the information in the sustainability-related disclosure section relates and prominently display the environmental or social characteristics or the sustainable investment objective of that financial product.*"

tory rules which must be followed, with the goal of being compliant with the ESG regulatory principles of equal treatment and well-informed investor. One of the newly introduced options was to have a set of disclosures available on the official fund's web-site (Busch, 2023: 3306), which allowed the prospectus of the fund to be subject to less changes in the event of product changes.

In terms of the oversight activity at the EU level, the European Securities and Markets Authority (ESMA)³³ is an independent EU authority that aims to enhance investor protection and promote stable and orderly financial markets (Lafarge, 2013: 1) by evaluating the compliance of the market participants with the sustainable framework. Its involvement with SFDR products entails ensuring that the ESG products which are marketed in the EU fulfill the set standards of transparency and investor protection. The ESMA issues: (i) opinions and responses on the frequently asked questions, in order to avoid any ambiguity, and (ii) formal reports, highlighting the areas which have room for improvement (ESMA, 2025).

In national jurisdictions, competent authorities are country-level regulators, such as *L'Autorité des marchés financiers* (AMF) in France, and *Bundesanstalt für Finanzdienstleistungsaufsicht* (BaFin) in Germany. They all have a common supervisory objective to ensure that the ESG funds comply with the SFDR's principles. In addition, national jurisdictions have created a labeling system by means of a formal certification, which assure that an ESG product meets the requirements. Product labeling regimes exist in Belgium (Febelfin label), France (ISR label), Germany, Switzerland (FNG-Siegel), etc. Unfortunately, the labelling regimes are neither harmonized nor aligned with each other. Thus, some of them ensure that a product meets minimum standards and exclusions (e.g. Febelfin label), while others additionally have to meet scoring requirements (e.g. FNG-Siegel) or ESG performance and benchmark (e.g. ISR label).

For the purpose of tracking the ESG funds, a digital platform "Morningstar" was designed to assist the investors, fund managers and financial advisors (Demartini, 2020: 15). This platform contains tools and services for reviewing the ESG factors (ESG investment portfolios, sustainable investment framework), overall ESG research (ESG data and metrics) and ratings (the reporting solutions).

³³ ESMA (2025). European Securities and Markets Authority, official web-site: <https://www.esma.europa.eu/>; <https://www.esma.europa.eu/about-esma>

6. The influence of sustainable strategies from the retail investor's perception

Over the past decade, the pro-environmental investments within the environmental and financial sectors had been increasing in demand from both institutional³⁴ and retail investors³⁵; nevertheless, the participation of retail investors has remained limited (Akhtar, 2019:14). The environmental and financial sectors may not seem to have anything in common at first but, as green initiatives are now becoming a requirement for major market leaders, their underlying and consumer-driven initiatives share the same interest on sustainability factors (Musciano, 2022: 436). One of the main challenges in practice is the fact that the sustainable investments are not a standardized one-size-fits-all product (Hauff, Nilsson, 2022: 1190); therefore, they need to be tailored on the basis of the selected jurisdiction, target investors and investment objective. The transition of green products require massive investments from both public and private sectors, making it crucial to remain very popular within the market for sustainable investments (Fricke, Schlepper, 2024: 1). Thus, the interest in the product which is initially maintained for institutional investors is an increasingly popular trend with retail investors (Mitić, 2024: 226).

The Morningstar's Sustainability Rating provides strong evidence that retail investors shift money away from low-rated and into high-rated funds (Becker, Martin, Walter, 2022: 3). The retail investors find environmental and social issues to be more important (Abhayawansa, Mooneeapen, 2022:319), for which reason the sustainable funds are becoming higher in demand. In addition, unlike conventional financial investing that focuses on the financial return alone, sustainable investing strives to generate measurable social returns and achieve financial market returns on a long-term basis (Liu, 2023: 162).

³⁴ *"The group of professional (qualified) investors includes: (a) institutional investors such as financial institutions, investment banks, investment companies, investment funds, insurance companies, pension funds, wealthy family companies, trusts (Bouchakour, 2010:4); (b) large undertakings meeting the specific size and revenue criteria; and (c) national and regional governments and public bodies, central banks, international and supranational institutions, and other institutional investors in financial instruments and transactions"* (MiFiD II, Annex II, section 1 "Categories of clients who are considered to be professionals"; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2014/65/oj/eng>).

³⁵ *On the other hand, "retail investors are non-professional investors (e.g. private individual investors) who do not (i) meet the criteria as defined under Annex II of MiFiD I; (ii) nor have the expertise and experience of professional investors but may be allowed (upon an extensive assessment and aptitude test) to act as investors"* (MiFiD II, Annex II, section 1).

Given the trend of rapid growth of sustainable investment funds, the issue of inconsistent and unregulated disclosures which most commonly lead to retail investor confusion and risk of greenwashing must be appropriately surpassed. Misleading of retail investors (by greenwashing) may create an unwanted effect of diverting them from sustainable products as they may be labeled as a high-risk and harmful investment. To prevent such outcomes, EU regulators should enforce a standardized set of ESG disclosure frameworks to ensure transparency, as well as a standardized set of labeling to ensure compliance and accuracy with the SFDR and avoid investor confusion. Such a standardized set of rules and labeling at the EU level should ensure that the AIFMs/ManCoscan appropriately protect the interest of the retail investors who rely on them to follow the product's objectives and policies (Musciano, 2022: 448).

7. Discussion and conclusion

In view of the recorded growth and impact of sustainable funds/products influencing constant changes in the EU's market, precise legal framework is crucial. As sustainable investments had been a cornerstone for the EU fund's strategies over the past few years, it may be argued that some areas are bound for improvement upon regulatory reviews and industry feedback. Clear and precise product reform could preclude possible classification misunderstanding. The current classification provided in Articles 6, 8 and 9 of the SFDR may lead to greenwashing risks. However, if the classification were to be reduced to two categories (sustainable and transition), it may enhance the investor protection.

Simplification and better standardization of the overall classification at the national level may lead to easier and better practice. From the marketing perspective, the misalignment of the labels between different EU states may lead to unwanted risks and challenges. The divergence of SFDR labeling may lead to investor confusion and mistrust, higher greenwashing risks, and unneeded operational complexity. Should an investor be used to one EU Member State's labeling regime, a differing regime in another EU Member State may raise suspicion and mistrust, resulting in the investor's avoidance of such product. In addition, the different SFDR labeling may enable greenwashing within the sustainable products, as it could make the assessment and supervision process more complex. Should the monitoring of the common multinational fund structures containing sustainable products be more demanding, the overall insurance of its compliance with the sustainable framework could be put at risk. Moreover, the cross-border fund structures may have duplicative compliance and operating burdens that may create conflicting expectations for the investors, which consequently may not want to be part of such products.

Considering the amount of input EU and its Member States have exerted since 2019 in the accomplishment of the European Green Deal, one may ask if the outcome would outperform and justify the exerted efforts and costs made. If the EU successfully performs its plan, creates its sustainable future and become the first climate-neutral region by 2050, there is still no guarantee that it would have any impact on the World. As one of the goals is to become a leader in the sustainable finance and a powerful example to others, there is no guarantee that it would create the wanted influence on the overall global market and standards, legal framework, climate diplomacy and development aid. Should it create the wanted effect and should the majority of the world start aligning their legal frameworks with the EU framework, this would consequently mean that all technology, renewable energy, sustainable finance, health and aid used today would be subject to change. In this event, the global impact would be profound.

In case no other countries outside the EU implement the sustainable framework within its jurisdictions or re-consider and implement it, but the EU would continue to enforce it, this could raise a question whether it would have any effect on the global scale if the EU would reduce only a minor percentage of global gas emissions. This is why it is of great importance to follow global market trends and the overall interest in the sustainable development by other non-EU countries. Considering that the efforts and costs of the EU's sustainability goals should ultimately be proportionate to the gained results, if the EU's actions would possibly have a negligible impact on the global scale, it is worth questioning whether the current actions are justified.

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ОДРЖИВИ ИНВЕСТИЦИОНИ ФОНДОВИ У ЕВРОПСКОЈ УНИЈИ

Резиме

Овај рад представља резултате емпиријског истраживања о правном уређењу одрживих инвестиционих фондова у Европској Унији. Након кратког историјата правног уређења одрживих инвестиционих фондова у Европској Унији, у првом делу рада се конкретно анализира Уредба ЕУ о објављивању информација о одрживим финансијама (СФДР) и други слични правни извори који додатно уређују област одрживих инвестиционих фондова. У другом делу рада аутор говори о потенцијалним елементима за детаљније уређење ове области.

Кључне речи: *Европска унија, одрживи инвестициони фонд, Уредба ЕУ о објављивању информација о одрживим финансијама (СФДР).*